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of EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

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Reasons Behind

Why do people commit crime?
A question that pauses time
Notable people have reached their prime
In giving answers that cost dime

Everyone has their reasons behind
Some have been treacherously blind
On the concept of being the mastermind
Pushing people to embrace and act with maligned

Some are involved in the crime of passion
Putting in mind that killing is the only solution
To end the miseries brought by their emotions
And be free from any feelings of depression

Some commits crime due to hedonism
Perpetrating rape, murder and arson are their naturalism
Embracing evil as their existentialism
Knowing that it is one of the acts of abnormalism

Most common reason of all times
It is poverty that pushes them to do crime
To survive every day and feed their hungry spare tire
And be at ease just one more time

Why do people commit crime?
Answers are laid down every time
Those that we can and can't understand at times
But in the end, we will be judged in a perfect time.